
Welcome to the CSCCE Community of Practice!

We're happy you're here! This document is intended to help you to get started in the CSCCE community of practice by highlighting some key links and activities. If you ever have questions, please don't hesitate to contact us by email at info@cscce.org, or by direct messaging Lou or Katie on Slack.

TL:DR - key links

- Slack channels - see below
- Archive of Community Call notes: [LINK REMOVED FOR PUBLIC DOCUMENT]
- Other shared notes (e.g., from external conferences and webinars): [LINK REMOVED FOR PUBLIC DOCUMENT]
- Events calendar: <https://www.cscce.org/calendar/>
- YouTube channel: https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCOv5_NsHDjyCjNafT4iPGVQ
- X account: [@TheCSCCE](https://twitter.com/TheCSCCE)
- Mastodon account: [@TheCSCCE@mastodon.online](https://mstdn.social/@TheCSCCE)
- Bluesky account: [@thescsccce.bsky.social](https://bsky.app/profile/thescsccce.bsky.social)
- LinkedIn page: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/cscce>
- Zenodo collection of downloadable resources: <https://zenodo.org/communities/cscce/>
- Curated resource pages: <https://www.cscce.org/resources/>
- Blog: <https://www.cscce.org/blog/>
- Policies and guides including community participation guidelines: <https://www.cscce.org/about-cscce/policies-and-guides/>

Slack

Slack is where our community members connect, and where we share CSCCE resources and opportunities to participate. If Slack is new to you, our [Slack Quick Start Guide](#) will help you set up your profile and workspace, and give you an overview of how we use the platform on a day-to-day basis.

DEFAULT CHANNELS

All new members are automatically added to:

#community - This is the main channel for general topics related to scientific community management. Everyone can post here.

#cop_admin_updates - This is a channel for CSCCE staff to share resources from the community calls and beyond.

#welcome - This channel is where new members post short bios about themselves - you're encouraged to say hello to others here!

OPTIONAL CHANNELS

There are additionally a growing number of optional channels. You can browse these by clicking on the channels title in the left-hand sidebar of Slack (see image, right). You're welcome to join any public channel within the CSCCE Slack workspace.

#books - This is a place to discuss books (and podcasts!) about community management and leadership. Also home to pop-up book clubs.

#champions_programs_sig - This is a special interest group for members to share resources, troubleshoot issues, and ask questions related to the launch and running of community champions programs.

#coffee_and-donuts - In this channel the Donut bot sets up one-to-one coffee chats every two weeks as a way for members to get to know each other and then share something interesting they discussed.

#covid_resources - Created in response to the global pandemic, this channel is for sharing links, advice, and other help as we all figure things out.

#coworking - This channel is for finding coworking partners and setting up sessions.

#data_science_sig - A special interest group for community managers from data science, data science adjacent, and data science interested communities to gather and share activities, updates, and observations.

#diversity_equity_inclusion_sig - This is a special interest group focused on diversity, equity and inclusion in scientific community-building.

#open_research_sig - A special interest group for people involved in coordinating and promoting open research practices to network, support, share information, experiences and advice.

#open_source_sig - A special interest group channel for everything at the intersection of community and open source! Co-admins: Sara Petti and Bri Johns

#jobs - A place to add jobs and other opportunities of relevance to the CSCCE community.

#measuring_impact - This channel was set up to discuss surveys and other means of assessment.

#pets - By popular demand, this channel is a place for light relief in the form of pictures of your pets (and plants, legos, etc...).

#random - Non-work banter and water cooler conversation.

#shared_joy - A channel to celebrate wins, share joy and exchange high fives.

#webinars-and-events - This channel is a place to share webinars, events, conferences and other gatherings that may be of interest to CSCCE community members.

#work_out_loud - We **#work_out_loud** on Mondays, although sometimes we use this channel on other days. Working out loud (e.g., by sharing your to do list, a project that's going really well, or something you're struggling with) is a great way to connect over shared issues, feel inspired by the

way others are managing their workflows, or provide a sense of accountability.

WEEKLY ROUNDUP EMAIL

Every Wednesday we share an email recap of what's going on in our Slack workspace. All Slack members receive this email, but if you would like to opt-out of this service please let us know by emailing info@cscce.org (note: unsubscribing via MailChimp will also remove you from our monthly newsletter mailing list). Here's [how we source and include content](#) in this weekly email.

Monthly Community Calls

As part of our programming to nurture a community of scientific community engagement managers and those interested in scientific community engagement, we host a monthly community call via Zoom. Usually held on the third Wednesday of the month* at 11am US Eastern Time, our monthly community calls are 90 minutes long and address a new theme each month. You can find [details of our past and future community calls on our website](#), and download calendar invites to future calls from our [events calendar](#).

**Sometimes speaker availability means that we shift day, time, or week.*

ARCHIVE OF COLLABORATIVE NOTES

For every call, we host a collaborative notes document for all participants to add their notes, questions, and additional resources. The documents are converted to view only after the calls and you can find these documents in this Google Drive folder [LINK REMOVED FOR PUBLIC DOCUMENT].

VIDEO ARCHIVE

We record the presentation section of our calls, and post archives of the individual presentations on our [YouTube channel](#). The discussion section, however, is not recorded. We regularly recap the calls [on our blog](#).

Monthly Newsletter

All members are automatically subscribed to receive our monthly newsletter. You can view past newsletters [in our archive](#). If you are concerned that you are not receiving this newsletter, or other email-related communications from us, please let Katie know either by direct message on Slack or by email to katie.pratt@cscce.org.

Co-creating with the CSCCE

We regularly collaborate with members of our community of practice to create materials such as guidebooks, tip sheets, and infographics. Watch out for invites to the next project in the #cop_admin_updates channel.

We also have a standing and open invitation to all members to contribute guest posts to [our blog](#).

To support these activities, we created:

- [Guidelines for contributions to CSCCE community resources](#)
- [An overview of how we credit contributions to CSCCE](#)
- [Guidelines for contributing to the CSCCE blog](#)
- [Guest blog style guide](#)
- [One pager or tip sheet style guide](#)
- [Report or guidebook style guide](#)

All contributors are asked to carefully read relevant documentation before submitting to, or signing off on, a project.

Working groups and special interest groups

CSCCE currently hosts a small number of [working groups](#) and [special interest groups](#). Participation in working groups occurs in private Slack channels, which we will advertise when the group is started and at intervals afterwards. Anyone is welcome to join a special interest group. If, after perusing the groups already in existence, you would like to propose a new working group or special interest group, you can do so by [filling in this form](#). For more on CSCCE's expectations of working group and special interest group co-chairs, please [read this guide](#).

Resources

Our website is home to a [suite of resources](#) for scientific community managers. Each of our resource pages includes links to guidebooks, one-pagers, and curated blog posts that cover everything from organizing online and in-person events, to nurturing diverse, equitable, and inclusive communities, and hiring a community management professional.

Giving credit

As outlined in our [core values](#), we expect our members to credit others' ideas and contributions if they are shared both inside and outside of the Slack workspace. This includes, but is not limited to:

- Crediting by @mentioning in online forums
- Crediting with an attribution in presentations or interviews
- Referring back to resources, with a link if possible

We also expect members to adhere to the licenses used on CSCCE outputs. If you have questions or wish to request additional permissions please get in touch.

Policies and guides

You can find all of CSCCE's [policies and guides](#) on our website. Everything that we do is guided by our [core values](#) and they underpin our community participation guidelines.

We hope you enjoy participating in the CSCCE community!

Please reach out with any questions or comments: info@cscce.org.

Citing and reusing this tip sheet

CITATION AND REUSE

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